

Optimization of some physical and chemical parameters on growth and production of lipase by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀

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Manuscript received 25 October 2010, accepted 16 November 2010

Abstract : The present study was carried out to maximize the production of lipase by a mutant strain of fungus - *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀, developed in our laboratory by induced mutation from parent strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* isolated from the soil collected from North Bengal. For this purpose different physicochemical parameters were optimized one by one. Maximum yield was obtained with 100 ml fermentation medium, initial pH 3.5, ml of inoculum size (containing 8.0×10^4 spores/ml), 6 days old inoculum, 72 h fermentation period, at 30 °C with 2.0% glucose as carbon and 0.7% urea as nitrogen sources. The production was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 666.66 to 1083.33 $\mu\text{M FFA/ml/min}$. The relative activity was also increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) from 100.00 to 167.63%. But the dry cell weight did not show any significant change.

Keywords : *Rhizopus arrhizus*, lipase.

Introduction

Lipases (EC 3.1.1.3), triacylglycerol acylhydrolases are widely distributed in various animals, plants and microorganisms. Lipase can catalyze the hydrolysis of triglycerides into mono- and diglycerides, glycerol and free fatty acids. Some lipases are also capable of catalyzing transesterification and enantioselective hydrolytic reactions¹. Microbial lipases have practical application in the oils, fats, dairy industries² and medicine³. Microbial lipase production had been widely reported by a variety of microorganisms including *Aspergillus niger*⁴, *Geotrichum candidum*⁵, *Rhizopus arrhizus*⁶, *Candida rugosa*⁷ and *Pseudomonas fragi*⁸. Several investigations had also been done on the effect of various physico-chemical parameters on lipase production⁹⁻¹⁹.

Considering the different reviews on optimization of various physico-chemical parameters on lipase production, in the present study different physico-chemical parameters were optimized one by one to maximize the lipase accumulation in the fermentation broth by a mutant *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ developed in our laboratory from the parent strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* by induced mutation using UV-irradiation as physical and ethyleneimine as chemical mutagens.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism : A fungal mutant *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ was developed in our laboratory from the parent strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* isolated from North Bengal soil by induced mutation using UV-irradiation as physical and ethyleneimine as chemical mutagens²⁰. The mutant strain was used throughout the study.

Medium : The mutant strain was maintained in Potato-Dextrose-Agar medium. The medium of (w/v) : K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; urea, 0.6%; KCl, MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.05% and castor oil (as inducer), 1.0%. Glucose was sterilized separately and added to the fermentation medium at concentration of 2.0%.

Inoculum : Inoculum was prepared by washing the spores of 6 days old in the P.D. Agar Slant with Sterile distilled water and the inoculums contained 8.0×10^4 spores/ml.

Culture conditions : 100 ml fermentation medium was taken in a 250 ml conical flask. Initial pH was adjusted to 4.0. For fermentative production of lipase, the medium was inoculated with 5 ml inoculum. Shake culture fermentation was adopted for production of lipase with rotational speed of 150 rpm. Duration of incubation was 3 days at 30 °C.

Determination of lipolytic activity : Lipolytic activities in the filtrates of fermentation broth were determined by the method as developed by Renshaw and San Clemente²¹. Lipase activity was expressed as μmol of free fatty acids liberated/ ml/min (μM FFA/ ml/min).

Determination of dry cell weight (DCW) : Dry cell weights of the spores were determined by the method of Shah *et al.*²².

Statistical analysis : All data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$. The data were analysed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post hoc multiple comparison test using "prism 4.0" soft ware (Graph pad Inc., USA). A "p" value less than 0.05 was considered as significant and less than 0.01 was considered as highly significant.

Results and discussion

Physical parameters :

Effect of incubation period on lipase production : Fermentation was carried out at different period of incubation (viz. 24, 48, 60, 72, 96 and 120 h) and maximum lipase production was obtained after 72 h of incubation (Fig. 1). This was probably due to the fact that at this stage of fermentation the growth of fungus was in the log

Fig. 1. Effect of period of incubation on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

phase and it produced maximum amount of lipase. Cell growth was also maximum after 72 h of incubation.

Effect of volume of fermentation medium : Fermentations were carried out using different volumes (viz. 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 ml) of fermentation media keeping all the other constituents constant and it was observed that maximum production of lipase occurred when media volume was 100 ml (Fig. 2). Reason may be the nutritional requirements in 100 ml medium was appropriate

Fig. 2. Effect of volume of fermentation medium for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

for the growth of spores present in 5 ml inoculum. Cellular growth was also maximum in 100 ml medium.

Effect of initial pH of the fermentation medium : To find out the optimum pH for the production of lipase by this mutant six different pH values (3.0-5.5) were used for the fermentation broth. pH were adjusted using 1.0 (N) HCl or NaOH. Production of lipase was maximum at pH 3.5 (Fig. 3) along with maximum cell growth.

Effect of temperature on fermentation : Temperature plays an important role on lipase production^{9,10,14}. To find out a suitable temperature for lipase production by this mutant strain, experiments were carried out at various temperatures (25, 28, 30, 33 and 35 °C). A temperature of 30 °C optimally favored the maximum lipase production (Fig. 4).

Effect of volume of inoculum : Inoculum volume is an essential physical parameter for microbial production of lipase. Several experiments were carried out using 3.0,

Fig. 3. Effect of initial pH of fermentation medium for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 5. Effect of volume of inoculum added to the fermentation medium for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

4.0, 5.0, 7.0 and 10.0% (v/v) inoculum volume each containing 8.0×10^4 spores/ml. Maximum yield along with highest cell density with 5.0% inoculum volume (Fig. 5).

Effect of age of inoculum : Age of inoculum was also another important factor for microbial lipase production¹². It has been observed that lipase production was also maxi-

imum with 6 days old inoculum. Cell growth was also maximum (Fig. 6). This may be due to the fact that at 6 days of incubation, the organism was in the log phase and maximum enzyme production was occurred at this stage. Younger cultures may not reach the log phase and older cultures may have proceeded to decline.

Fig. 6. Effect of age of inoculum on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Chemical parameters :

Effect of different carbon sources : Several carbon sources were tested for lipase production (Fig. 7) and

Fig. 7. Determination of suitable carbon source for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

among all the sources, glucose was proved to be the best carbon source utilized for lipase production by the particular mutant strain. The reason may be due to easily utilization of glucose than other carbon sources. Cellular growth was also maximum in case of glucose as carbon source.

It had been observed that among different concentrations tested, 2.0% glucose was proved to be optimum for the fermentative production of lipase by this mutant. Cell growth was also maximum in case of 2.0% glucose as entire carbon source (Fig. 8). This is probably because lower concentration of glucose is insufficient for cellular growth and due to hyper osmotic nature of glucose, it exerts detrimental effects on spores, leading to decrease production of the enzyme¹⁶.

Fig. 8. Determination of optimum glucose concentration for maximum production of lipase by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Effect of different nitrogen sources : Several nitrogen sources were examined to find out the suitable nitrogen source for lipase production by this mutant, among which urea was proved to be the best nitrogen source utilized by this organism for lipase fermentation (Fig. 9).

To optimize the urea concentration for this fermentation, different concentrations ranging from 0.4–0.8% were

studied. 0.6% concentration was proved to be most suitable for lipase production by this strain along with maximum cell growth (Fig. 10).

Production falls above and below this concentration. This is probably because, lower concentration of urea is insufficient for cell growth and enzyme production, where

Fig. 9. Determination of suitable nitrogen source for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 10. Optimization of urea concentration for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

as higher concentrations of urea exert osmotic pressure, leading to spore damage¹⁹.

Therefore after optimization of different physico-chemical parameters for lipase fermentation by the mutant *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀, the lipolytic activity (indicator of lipase production) was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 666.66 to 1083.33 μ M FFA/ml/min. The relative activity was also increased significant ($p < 0.05$) from 100.00 to 167.63%. But the dry cell weight increase did not show significant changes compared to control.

Conclusion :

After optimization of different physico-chemical parameters, the lipolytic activity (indicator of lipase production) was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 666.66 to 1083.33 with 100 ml fermentation medium; initial pH adjusted to 3.5; 5 ml of inoculum size (containing 8×10^4 spores/ml); 6 days old inoculum; incubation was carried out at 30 °C for 3 days in shake flask culture method using 2.0% glucose as carbon and 0.7% urea as nitrogen sources.

Acknowledgement

We express our sincere gratitude to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for their continuous financial support throughout the research work.

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